
Involving employee performance in the influence of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership on employee motivation at the South Konawe Revenue Agency

Rasnawati^{1*}, Nurwati², Yusuf Montundu³

Universitas Halu Oleo, Indonesia¹

Universitas Halu Oleo, Indonesia²

Universitas Halu Oleo, Indonesia³

Corresponding Email: rasnawatialeumdaun@gmail.com*

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership on the performance and work motivation of employees at the Regional Revenue Agency of South Konawe Regency, with a total of 61 employees. The method used was SEM-PLS analysis with data collected through questionnaires. The results of the study show that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, especially in managing workload, effective communication, and harmonious working relationships. Meanwhile, transformational leadership also improves employee performance through individualized attention, role modeling, motivation, and intellectual stimulation. Emotional intelligence also increased work motivation, but the influence of transformational leadership on work motivation was not significant, suggesting the variability of its effectiveness depending on the specific situation. Employee performance plays a significant role in increasing work motivation, both directly and as a mediator in the relationship of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership to work motivation.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Transformational Leadership, Performance, Motivation

Abstrak

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis pengaruh kecerdasan emosional dan kepemimpinan transformasional terhadap kinerja serta motivasi kerja pegawai di Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Konawe Selatan, dengan jumlah objek sebanyak 61 pegawai. Metode yang digunakan adalah analisis SEM-PLS dengan data yang dikumpulkan melalui kuesioner. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa kecerdasan emosional berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap kinerja pegawai, terutama dalam mengelola beban kerja, komunikasi yang efektif, dan hubungan kerja yang harmonis. Sementara itu, kepemimpinan

transformatif juga meningkatkan kinerja pegawai melalui perhatian individual, keteladanan, motivasi, dan stimulasi intelektual. Kecerdasan emosional juga meningkatkan motivasi kerja, namun pengaruh kepemimpinan transformatif terhadap motivasi kerja tidak signifikan, menunjukkan variabilitas efektivitasnya tergantung pada situasi spesifik. Kinerja pegawai berperan signifikan dalam meningkatkan motivasi kerja, baik secara langsung maupun sebagai mediator dalam hubungan kecerdasan emosional dan kepemimpinan transformatif terhadap motivasi kerja.

Kata kunci: *Kecerdasan Emosional, Kepemimpinan Transformatif, Kinerja, Motivasi*

Introduction

An organization serves as an entity that coordinates and directs joint efforts to achieve set goals. To achieve these goals, organizations depend on the quality and contributions of the individuals involved in them (Sobirin, 2014). Therefore, motivating human resources to give their best is a major concern for organizational management. To run an organization, a motivational factor is needed.

Luthans (2011) Motivation is a process that starts from a physiological or psychological deficiency or need that activates a behavior or drive aimed at a goal or incentive. Thus, the key to understanding the motivational process lies in meaning, and the relationship between needs, motivations, and incentives. Motivation is defined as a set of strengths Energy that comes from within and outside an employee, initiates work-related endeavors, and determines the direction, intensity, and his perseverance (Singh & Ramdeo, 2023). Motivation is an important consideration because effective job performance is often important. requires a high level of ability and motivation (Troia et al., 2023).

Organizations have a crucial role in shaping and maintaining work motivation. In a competitive context, organizations are required to continue to adapt and improve their competitiveness. One way to achieve this is to ensure that human resources feel motivated to deliver their best quality of work at all times (Popoola & Fagbola, 2023). The challenge of building and maintaining high work motivation within the organization cannot be ignored either. High workloads, uncertainty in the work environment, lack of support from employers, as well as lack of opportunities for career development, can all reduce a person's motivation level (Sugiarti, 2024).

One of the factors that affects work motivation is emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to recognize, understand, manage, and express emotions wisely in a variety of social situations and interactions (Riza & Yoto, 2023). Emotional intelligence includes a number of essential skills to interact effectively with others, manage conflicts, make the right decisions, and manage yourself in the face of life's pressures and challenges.

The importance of emotional intelligence has been increasingly recognized in a variety of contexts, including in the workplace (Burhamzah et al., 2023). In the workplace, emotional intelligence is a key factor in determining a person's success in achieving individual and organizational goals. Individuals with high levels of Emotional Intelligence tend to be better

able to adapt to change, work in teams, build strong relationships with coworkers, and manage stress and pressure well (Fahrati & Pramukty, 2023).

Sanchez-Gomez and Bresó (2020) Emotional intelligence significantly increases work motivation. Individuals who have high levels of emotional intelligence tend to have higher intrinsic motivation because they are able to recognize and manage their emotions well. However, it is different from the findings Naik and Kiran (2018) Finding that emotional intelligence had no significant effect on improving work motivation.

Voon et al. (2011) The success of the organization in achieving goals and objectives depends on a leader in adopting the right leadership style so that it can affect productivity. Transformational leadership has an important role in increasing work motivation in an organization (Wen, 2021). One of the key keys to this leadership is his ability to influence and inspire subordinates with a clear and inspiring vision. A transformational leader is able to communicate this vision effectively to his or her team, thus providing a strong sense of meaning and purpose for each individual.

In addition, transformational leadership is also able to create a work environment full of enthusiasm and enthusiasm (Amaliah & Sakir, 2023). This type of leader often shows a positive attitude, optimism, and confidence in facing challenges. This optimistic attitude is contagious to team members, inspiring them to stay motivated and motivated despite the difficulties or obstacles in their work. Thus, transformational leadership not only provides a clear direction, but also helps to build a positive and pleasant work atmosphere, which can improve overall work motivation.

Prayudi (2020) transformational leadership is significant to work motivation. This type of leadership tends to encourage the development of individual potential. Meanwhile, in contrast to other findings, the type of transformational leadership has a non-significant impact on work motivation (Muljani et al., 2012; Tobing & Prihatini, 2016). Darmawan (2009) Explaining the performance and work motivation in this study can be used as a basis that the components of organizational behavior are the foundation for the behavior of each of its members. Employee performance is an important aspect in the context of an organization, which is closely related to work motivation (Tafonao, 2023). Satisfactory performance often has a positive impact on work motivation. Employees feel that their efforts and hard work are recognized and appreciated by the organization, this can increase their intrinsic motivation to continue to perform well.

This study will focus on the employees of the Regional Revenue Agency as one of the agencies in the South Konawe Regency Government has a function to support government affairs which is the regional authority in the field of tax, levy and regional revenue management as mandated about the position, organizational structure, duties and functions as well as the work procedures of the Regional Revenue Management Agency. So the purpose of the study is to examine the role of employee performance in mediating the influence of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership on employee work motivation.

Research Method

The design in this study uses a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach is a research approach that primarily uses *the post-positivism* paradigm in developing science (such as thinking about cause and effect, reduction to variables, hypotheses, specific questions, using measurement and observation, and theoretical testing) using research strategies such as experiments and surveys that require statistical data. This study uses a quantitative approach because the research instrument uses a questionnaire, and the respondents' responses will be grouped into score categories using the Likert scale range. The population of this study is Employees at the Regional Revenue Agency of South Konawe Regency. The number of employees who became the population of this study was 61 people.

Indicators of emotional intelligence Law et al. (2004) mentioned in Colquitt et al. (2015) including self-awareness, others awareness, emotion use), and emotion regulation. Transformational leadership Bass (1996) and Trottier et al. (2008) It consists of four individualized considerations, idealized influence, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation. Performance indicators Condrey (2005) Includes attachment to tasks/work, work attitudes, quality of work, initiative, cooperation, quantity of work, learning and self-development, leadership. Finally, work motivation indicators Osafo et al. (2021) Terdirid ari expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. Inferential data analysis using the concept of *Structural Equation Type* (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) program using *Smart PLS* and *Microsoft Excel*. The following presentation of respondent characteristic data aims to find out the specific characteristics of the respondent so that it makes it easier for researchers to conduct analysis as follows:

Table 1. Respondent characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	%
Age Group		
37-43	12	19,67
44-50	49	80,33
	61	100
Gender		
Man	34	55,74
Woman	27	44,26
	61	100
Eduacation level		
SMA	19	31,15
D-III	3	4,92
S-1	35	57,38
S-2	3	4,92
S.3	1	1,64
	61	100
Work experience		
4-14	35	57,38
15-25	24	39,34
26-36	2	3,28
	61	100

Table 1 provides an overview of the characteristics of respondents from the Regional Revenue Agency of South Konawe Regency. This table groups respondents by age group, gender, education level, and work experience, showing the frequency and percentage distribution for each category. The majority of respondents were in the age group of 44-50 years (80.33%), male (55.74%), have an S-1 education level (57.38%), and have work experience between 4-14 years (57.38%).

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Results of the Measurement Model

Variables	Items	Loadings	CR	CA	AVE
Emotional intelligence	X1.1	0,925	0,957	0,940	0,847
	X1.2	0,896			
	X1.3	0,887			
	X1.4	0,971			
Transformational leadership	X2.1	0,906	0,910	0,869	0,718
	X2.2	0,852			
	X2.3	0,791			
	X2.4	0,837			
Employee performance	Y1.1	0,857	0,946	0,934	0,687
	Y1.2	0,883			
	Y1.3	0,857			
	Y1.4	0,804			
	Y1.5	0,810			
	Y1.6	0,775			
Work motivation	Y1.7	0,777	0,900	0,940	0,750
	Y1.8	0,859			
	Y2.1	0,843			
	Y2.2	0,835			
	Y2.3	0,917			

This table shows the results of the validity and reliability analysis for the variables of emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, employee performance, and work motivation. Each variable has multiple items measured with high loadings values, indicating a strong correlation between the item and the variable being measured. Emotional intelligence (X1.1-X1.4) had loadings values between 0.887 to 0.971, with CR 0.957, CA 0.940, and AVE 0.847. Transformational leadership (X2.1-X2.4) had loadings values between 0.791 to 0.906, with CR 0.910, CA 0.869, and AVE 0.718. Employee performance (Y1.1-Y1.8) had loadings between 0.775 to 0.883, with CR 0.946, CA 0.934, and AVE 0.687. Work motivation (Y2.1-Y2.3) had a loadings value between 0.835 to 0.917, with CR 0.900, CA 0.940, and AVE 0.750. Overall, all variables showed high validity and reliability, indicated by CR values above 0.7, CA above 0.7, and AVE above 0.5.

Table 3. Discriminant validity (HTMT)

	1	2	3	4
1 Emotional intelligence				
2 Transformational leadership	0,519			
3 Employee performance	0,731	0,766		
4 Work motivation	0,777	0,697	0,875	

This table shows the validity of discrimination using the HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio) method for the variables of emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, employee performance, and work motivation. The HTMT value between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership was 0.519, with employee performance being 0.731, and with work motivation being 0.777. The HTMT value between transformational leadership and employee performance was 0.766 and with work motivation was 0.697. The HTMT value between employee performance and work motivation is 0.875. Overall, these HTMT values indicate that the constructs have sufficient discriminatory validity, with values generally below the threshold of 0.85 or 0.90, indicating that the constructs are quite different from each other.

Table 4. R-Square

	R Square
Employee performance (Y1)	0,666
Work motivation (Y2)	0,662

Source: Data processed, (2024)

With an R-Square value of 0.666 for employee performance (Y1) and 0.662 for work motivation (Y2), the table shows the results of the calculation of the total determination coefficient (Q^2) to test the feasibility of the model. Q-Square measures how well the observation values produced by the model and its parameter estimation. A Q-Square value greater than zero indicates that the model has predictive relevance, while a Q-Square less than zero indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. Based on the calculations, the Q-Square value of 0.887 can be interpreted that the employee performance model in mediating the influence of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership on employee work motivation has good predictive relevance, with 11.3% still explained by other variables.

Figure 1. Testing Result

Table 5. Hypothesis Test Results for direct relationship and indirect effect

Hypothesis	Direct Influence	Path Coefficient	P-values	Result
H1	Emotional Intelligence -> Employee Performance	0,476	0,000	Accepted
H2	Transformational Leadership -> Employee Performance	0,472	0,000	Accepted
H3	Emotional Intelligence -> Work Motivation	0,314	0,003	Accepted
H4	Transformational Leadership -> Work Motivation	0,113	0,214	Rejected
H5	Employee Performance -> Work Motivation Indirect Influence	0,479	0,002	Accepted
H6	Emotional Intelligence -> Employee Performance -> Work Motivation	0,228	0,007	<i>Partial Mediation</i>
H7	Transformational Leadership -> Employee Performance -> Work Motivation	0,226	0,017	<i>Perfect mediation</i>

Based on the results of the study, the influence of emotional intelligence on employee performance resulted in a path coefficient value of 0.476 ($\beta = 0.476$, $p = 0.000$), which means that there is a positive and significant influence between emotional intelligence and employee performance, so that the hypothesis proposed can be accepted. The influence of transformational leadership on employee performance resulted in a path coefficient value of 0.472 ($\beta = 0.472$, $p = 0.000$), showing a positive and significant influence, so this hypothesis was also accepted. The influence of emotional intelligence on work motivation resulted in a path coefficient value of 0.314 ($\beta = 0.314$, $p = 0.000$), showing a positive and significant influence, supporting the hypothesis proposed. On the contrary, the influence of transformational leadership on work motivation resulted in a path coefficient value of 0.113 ($\beta = 0.113$, $p = 0.214$), showing a positive but insignificant influence, so this hypothesis was not accepted. The influence of employee performance on work motivation resulted in a path coefficient value of 0.479 ($\beta = 0.479$, $p = 0.002$), showing a positive and significant influence, so this hypothesis was accepted. The direct influence of emotional intelligence on work motivation has a path coefficient value of 0.314 ($\beta = 0.314$, $p = 0.003$), and the indirect influence through employee performance has a path coefficient of 0.228 ($\beta = 0.228$, $p = 0.007$), indicating that the nature of the mediation is partial mediation. The direct influence of transformational leadership on work motivation has a path coefficient value of 0.113 ($\beta = 0.113$, $p = 0.214$), while the indirect influence through employee performance has a path coefficient of 0.226 ($\beta = 0.226$, $p = 0.017$), indicating that the nature of mediation is perfect mediation.

Based on the findings of this study, it is known that some influences are directly accepted and some are not accepted, Fitriastuti (2013) Explaining that emotional intelligence can affect performance in the workplace is through its ability to influence individual decisions and behavior. The results of previous studies support previous studies that suggest that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance (Chamizo-Nieto et al., 2021; Sanchez-Gomez & Bresó, 2020)

Chamizo-Nieto et al. (2021) transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Transformational leadership has a significant influence on performance (Alzoraiki et al., 2023; Marisya et al., 2023; Pamungkas et al., 2023). Emotional intelligence has a significant influence on employee work motivation. Setiawan et al. (2019) Workers have high emotional intelligence tend to feel more connected to their work and more committed to giving their best They have a strong intrinsic motivation to achieve job satisfaction and personal achievement, which ultimately increases their work motivation (Sandi et al., 2021).

Other findings also show significant transformational leadership in performance (Hasan et al., 2023). The findings of this study show that although transformational leadership has a positive influence on employee work motivation. Tobing and Prihatini (2016) His findings found that transformational leadership had an insignificant impact on work motivation. Transformational leadership styles are not appropriate or supportive to increase work motivation. Performance can have a relationship with employee motivation (Sokro, 2012). This is in line with the statement of Darmawan (2009) explaining that the performance and work motivation in this study can be used as the basis that the components of organizational behavior are the foundation for every behavior of its members. The findings in this study are relevant to the results of research from Tafonao (2023) Employee performance has a significant effect on work motivation.

The findings of this study show that the influence of emotional intelligence on work motivation is researched through two channels, direct and indirect. Emotional intelligence affects the way individuals respond and respond to various situations in the workplace. Individuals with high levels of emotional intelligence tend to be better able to understand their own emotions and those of others, which can help them manage stress, conflict, and pressure more effectively (Binsaeed et al., 2023; Fiori et al., 2023; Igbokwe et al., 2023). As such, individuals with good emotional intelligence may have better performance because they are better able to cope with challenges, avoid unnecessary conflicts, and stay focused on their goals.

The findings of this study show that employee performance mediates the influence of transformational leadership on work motivation. Transformational leadership influences employee behavior and motivation through various ways, such as providing inspiration, building a shared vision, and providing encouragement to innovate (Mohammed & AL-Abrow, 2023; Udin et al., 2023). Transformational leaders often show a high commitment to organizational goals and upheld values. Transformational leaders seek to understand individual needs and aspirations and provide the necessary support for personal and professional development (Kilag et al., 2024; Sliwka et al., 2024). When employees feel driven to create

and contribute in unique ways, it increases their intrinsic motivation to achieve exceptional results (Zhang & Bartol, 2010; Zhou & George, 2003).

Conclusion

In a study conducted at the Regional Revenue Agency of South Konawe Regency, it was found that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. A high level of emotional intelligence allows employees to better manage emotions, communicate effectively, and maintain harmonious working relationships, which in turn increases their work effectiveness. On the other hand, transformational leadership also shows a positive influence on employee performance, with leaders who are able to motivate, inspire, and stimulate subordinates to think and act more rationally, creating a supportive and motivating work environment. However, the study also shows that the influence of transformational leadership on employee motivation is not significant, indicating that this leadership style may not be fully effective in all operational conditions in Regional Revenue Agencies. This underscores the importance of adapting leadership styles according to the specific organizational context. In addition, this study reveals that employee performance plays a significant role as a mediator in the relationship between emotional intelligence and work motivation, as well as transformational leadership and work motivation, suggesting that improving employee performance can be an effective strategy to improve overall work motivation.

This study shows some limitations that are important to note in the follow-up study. First, because the research was conducted limited to employees of the Regional Revenue Agency of South Konawe Regency, the results obtained may not be generalized to all public organizations that have different structures or cultures. Second, the use of cross-sectional survey methods in data collection results in limitations in controlling and understanding variable changes over time. For this reason, further research is recommended to conduct studies in various public organizations using longitudinal methods that can monitor changes in the relationship between variables more effectively. Additionally, it can be beneficial to test other variables such as transactional or situational leadership to gain a deeper understanding of leadership dynamics and their effects on performance and work motivation.

References

- Alzoraiki, M., Ahmad, A. R., Ateeq, A. A., Naji, G. M. A., Almaamari, Q., & Beshr, B. A. H. (2023). Impact of teachers' commitment to the relationship between transformational leadership and sustainable teaching performance. *Sustainability*, *15*(5), 4620.
- Amaliah, Y., & Sakir, A. R. (2023). The Influence of Transformational Leadership on the Performance of the State Civil Apparatus at the Lamuru Sub-district Office, Bone Regency. *Journal of Public Relations*, *1*(3), 54-69.
- Bass, B. M. (1996). *New paradigm of leadership: An inquiry into transformational leadership*. U.S. Army Research Institute for the Behavioral and Social Sciences.

- Binsaeed, R. H., Yousaf, Z., Grigorescu, A., Condrea, E., & Nassani, A. A. (2023). Emotional Intelligence, Innovative Work Behavior, and Cultural Intelligence Reflection on Innovation Performance in the Healthcare Industry. *Brain Sciences*, *13*(7), 1071.
- Burhamzah, M., Novia, L., Fatimah, S., & Alam, A. (2023). Teacher Training for the Future: Developing Emotional Intelligence in the Classroom as the Key to 21st Century Education Success. *Jurnal Gembira: Community Service*, *1*(05), 1335-1344.
- Chamizo-Nieto, M. T., Arrivillaga, C., Rey, L., & Extremera, N. (2021). The role of emotional intelligence, the teacher-student relationship, and flourishing on academic performance in adolescents: a moderated mediation study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *12*, 695067.
- Colquitt, J. A., Lepine, J. A., & Wesson, M. J. (2015). *Organizational behavior: Improving performance and commitment*. *Organizational Behaviour*. McGraw-Hill Education. www.mhhe.children.
- Condrey, S. E. (2005). *Handbook of human resources management in government*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Darmawan, D. (2009). *Employee Behavior and Performance*. Metromedia Education Publisher, Surabaya.
- Fahrati, M., & Pramukty, R. (2023). Factors influencing the ethical behavior of auditors: intellectual ability, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence. *Jupiter: Balance of Management, Accounting, and Economics*, *1*(8), 101-110.
- Fiori, M., Vesely-Maillefer, A. K., Nicolet-Dit-Félix, M., & Gillioz, C. (2023). With great sensitivity comes great management: how emotional hypersensitivity can be the superpower of emotional intelligence. *Journal of Intelligence*, *11*(10), 198.
- Fitriastuti, T. (2013). The influence of emotional intelligence, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior on employee performance. *JDM (Journal of Management Dynamics)*, *4*(2).
- Hasan, A. A., Ahmad, S. Z., & Osman, A. (2023). Transformational leadership and work engagement as mediators on nurses' job performance in healthcare clinics: work environment as a moderator. *Leadership in Health Services*, *36*(4), 537-561.
- Igbokwe, I. C., Egboka, P. N., Thompson, C. C., Etele, A. V., Anyanwu, A. N., Okeke-James, N. J., & Uzoekwe, H. E. (2023). Emotional intelligence: practices to manage and develop it. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, *1*(4), 42-48.
- Kilag, O. K., Malbas, M., Nengasca, M. K., Longakit, L. J., Celin, L., Pasigui, R., & Valenzona, M. A. V. (2024). Transformational Leadership and Educational Innovation. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, *1*(1), 110-114.
- Law, K. S., Wong, C.-S., & Song, L. J. (2004). The construct and criterion validity of emotional intelligence and its potential utility for management studies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, *89*(3), 483.
- Luthans, F. (2011). *Organizational behavior an evidence-based approach 12th edition the twelfth edition of organizational behavior: An evidence-based approach is ideal for*. In.

- Marisyah, F., Mayasari, V., Astuti, S. D., & Purwanto, M. B. (2023). Implementation of Leadership Ethics and Transformational Leadership in Employee Performance. *Asian Journal of Applied Business and Management*, 2(4), 545-556.
- Mohammed, A. A., & AL-Abrow, H. (2023). The impact of empowering and transformational leadership on organizational performance and innovation: the mediating role of shared leadership and moderating role of organizational culture in the Iraqi healthcare sector. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 31(7), 3532-3552.
- Muljani, B. D., Alhabsji, T., & Hamid, D. (2012). The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Quality of Work Life on Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction (Study on Educators Led by Women Leaders at Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya). *Profit: Journal of Business Administration*, 6(2).
- Naik, D., & Kiran, D. A. (2018). Emotional intelligence and achievement motivation among college students. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing*, 9(1), 86-88.
- Osafo, E., Paros, A., & Yawson, R. M. (2021). Valence–instrumentality–expectancy model of motivation as an alternative model for examining ethical leadership behaviors. *SAGE Open*, 11(2), 21582440211021896.
- Pamungkas, B. C., Brahmasari, I. A., & Ratih, I. A. B. (2023). The Effect Of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture, And Management Control System On Employee Performance With Organizational Commitment As The Intervening Variable At CV Makmur Jaya Abadi Surabaya City. *J. Econ. Financ. Manag. Stud*, 6, 429-437.
- Popoola, S. O., & Fagbola, O. O. (2023). Work motivation, job satisfaction, work-family balance, and job commitment of library personnel in Universities in North-Central Nigeria. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 49(4), 102741.
- Prayudi, A. (2020). The effect of transformational leadership style on employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable (a study on employees pd. Development of Binjai City). *JOURNAL MANAGEMENT*, 1(2), 63-72.
- Riza, F., & Yoto, Y. (2023). Building the Emotional Intelligence of Vocational School Students to Answer the Challenges of Modern Industry. *Brilliant: Journal of Research and Conceptual*, 8(4), 940-947.
- Sanchez-Gomez, M., & Bresó, E. (2020). In pursuit of work performance: Testing the contribution of emotional intelligence and burnout. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(15), 5373.
- Sandi, H., Afni Yunita, N., Heikal, M., Nur Ilham, R., & Sinta, I. (2021). Relationship Between Budget Participation, Job Characteristics, Emotional Intelligence and Work Motivation As Mediator Variables to Strengthening User Power Performance: An Emperical Evidence From Indonesia Government. *Morfai Journal*, 1(1), 36-48.
- Setiawan, I. A., Sulistiyowati, L. N., & Hasanah, K. (2019). The influence of emotional intelligence, organizational commitment, work motivation and organizational citizenship behavior on the performance of BPR Tunas Artha Jaya Abadi Mejayan Branch employees. SIMBA: Management, Business, and Accounting Innovation Seminar,
- Singh, R., & Ramdeo, S. (2023). Employee Motivation in a Changing Environment. In *Contemporary Perspectives in Human Resource Management and Organizational*

Behavior: Research Overviews and Gaps to Advance Interrelated Fields (pp. 191-208). Springer.

- Sliwka, A., Klopsch, B., Beigel, J., & Tung, L. (2024). Transformational leadership for deeper learning: shaping innovative school practices for enhanced learning. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 62(1), 103-121.
- Sobirin, A. (2014). Organization and Organizational Behavior. *Organizational Culture, Definition, Meaning and Application*, 1, 72.
- Sokro, E. (2012). Analysis of the relationship that exists between organisational culture, motivation and performance. *Problems of Management in the 21st Century*, 3(1), 106-119.
- Sugiarti, E. (2024). The Impact of Workload and Negative Work Environment on Employee Work Motivation. *ACADEMIC: Economics & Business Student Journal*, 4(1), 385-396.
- Tafonao, Y. (2023). The Relationship of Performance Assessment to Employee Work Motivation at the Gomo Sub-district Office, South Nias Regency. *South Nias Student Scientific Journal*, 6(1), 118-129.
- Tobing, D. S., & Prihatini, D. (2016). The influence of mutation, organizational culture and transformational leadership on work motivation and employee performance at state wealth service offices and auctions in the East Java Province area. *BISMA: Journal of Business and Management*, 10(1), 41-54.
- Troia, G. A., Shankland, R. K., & Wolbers, K. A. (2023). Motivation research in writing: Theoretical and empirical considerations. *Motivating Writers in Class*, 5-28.
- Trottier, T., Van Wart, M., & Wang, X. (2008). Examining the nature and significance of leadership in government organizations. *Public administration review*, 68(2), 319-333.
- Udin, U., Dharma, R. D., Dananjoyo, R., & Shaikh, M. (2023). The Role of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance Through Organizational Learning Culture and Intrinsic Work Motivation. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & Planning*, 18(1).
- Voon, M. L., Lo, M. C., Ngui, K. S., & Ayob, N. B. (2011). The influence of leadership styles on employees' job satisfaction in public sector organizations in Malaysia. *International journal of business, management and social sciences*, 2(1), 24-32.
- Wen, G. (2021). The Influence of Transformational and Transactional Leadership on Work Motivation and Work Performance of Structural Officials of the Mappi Regency Education Office. *Journal of Law, Humanities and Politics*, 2(1), 51-57.
- Zhang, X., & Bartol, K. M. (2010). Linking empowering leadership and employee creativity: The influence of psychological empowerment, intrinsic motivation, and creative process engagement. *Academy of Management journal*, 53(1), 107-128.
- Zhou, J., & George, J. M. (2003). Awakening employee creativity: The role of leader emotional intelligence. *The leadership quarterly*, 14(4-5), 545-568.